

Amylase from Sweet Potato (*Ipomoea Batatas*).

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Among plant amylases, those from leaves and grains have been most studied, but only comparatively meagre information is available regarding the nature and behaviour of amylases from tubers.

Payen and Persoz (*Annalen*, 1834, 53, 73 ; 56, 337) were the first to observe the presence of amylase in germinating potato, but very little fresh information was added by later workers. Chrzaszcz and Kostytschew, (*Woch. Barau.*, 1902, 25, 105), Kostytschew, (*Ber. Bot. Ges.*, 1913, 31, 125), Windisch and Jetter (*Z. Spiritusind*, 1907, 30, 554), Heinzelmann, (*ibid.*, 1908, 31, 12) until Doby (*Biochem. Z.*, 1914, 67, 166) and Doby and Burger (*Fermentforsche*, 1932, 13, 201) made a systematic study of the various factors that influence the activity of potato amylase.

The observations of Doby (*loc. cit.*) as also the later ones of Haehn and Schweigart (*Biochem. Z.*, 1923, 143, 516) led to the conclusion that potato amylase resembles animal amylases in its behaviour towards salts, amino acids, hydrogen-ion concentration and temperature changes. McGuire and Falk (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1920, 2, 215) have shown that the optimum reaction for potato amylase lies at p_H 6.7. Borchardt and Pringsheim (*Biochem. Z.*, 1931, 239, 193) obtained evidence to show that potato amylase occupies an intermediate position between the malt amylase which is particularly rich in β -amylase, and the taka-amylase which is pure α -amylase.

In view of the importance of the foregoing observations and the inadequacy of our knowledge regarding other tuber amylases, the present investigation on the amylase from sweet potato was undertaken.

Sweet potato is a common vegetable which is extensively cultivated in India. It is commonly used as food, cooked in curry or boiled, roasted or fried. Two forms are met with, one the red and the other the white tuber. Both the forms contain about 10 to 20% of sugar and about 16% of starch (*cf.* Watt, "The Commercial Products of India," 1908, p. 687).

The importance of the study of amylase present in sweet potato can be seen in the extensive application of the enzyme in industries like syrup manufacture, where it is employed to remove starch, which is responsible for the jellying and for the difficulty with which the syrup filters. In view of the possibilities of manufacturing syrup from sweet potato (Gore, Raese and Reed, *Chem. Age*, 1921, 29, 151) a knowledge of the characteristics and the rôle played by the amylase present in the tuber is of great value in controlling the conditions for successful operation of the method.

Gore (*Ann. Food J.*, 1923, 18, 519) has shown that maltose is formed on cooking sweet potato and this is attributed presumably to the presence of diastase in the tuber.

Hasselbring and Hawkins (*J. Agric. Res.*, 1915, 5, 331, 543) have investigated the general course of carbohydrate transformation in sweet potatoes, during storage, and observed that in the stored sweet potato starch is first converted into reducing sugars, and finally cane sugar is synthesised from reducing sugars. Here again a study of the rôle played by amylase present in the tuber is of great importance in elucidating the physiological changes taking place in the tuber during storage and germination.

The present communication relates to the characteristics and mode of action of the sweet potato amylase, its function in the tuber and finally its comparison with amylases from other sources.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of the enzyme.—For the larger part of this work fresh tubers (red variety) were obtained from the market. An active preparation of the amylase can be obtained by pressing the juice from the tuber in a hydraulic press. The juice thus obtained is a light brown and opalescent liquid, and contains the amylase. The juice does not, however, keep well, so other methods of preparing the enzyme from dry material had to be adopted.

After mincing the tuber in a chopper, the ground tissue was spread on enamelled trays and kept for drying in bright sun. By frequent turning, the material can be dried in 5-6 hours. The material should not be allowed to ferment, as the activity of the enzyme is generally reduced by fermentation. The sun dried material was ground to a fine powder and passed through a 40 mesh sieve. The powder can be preserved well in bottles without any loss of

amylolytic activity. The enzyme can be easily extracted from this powdered meal with water or aqueous glycerol. The extract can be purified by dialysis in collodion bags.

The enzyme can be obtained in a concentrated form by precipitation with alcohol from aqueous extracts of the meal. 200 G. of dry powdered meal were extracted with 800 c. c. of water for 12 hours in presence of toluene. It was then filtered and centrifuged. The amylase was precipitated from the aqueous extract by adding four times the volume of 95 % alcohol, and after the settling of the precipitate the top layer was syphoned off and the rest centrifuged. The sediment thus obtained was treated with absolute alcohol and ether and finally dried in a desiccator over anhydrous calcium chloride. The resultant powder is light brown in colour.

Methods of procedure.—Soluble starch prepared according to Zulkowsky was used as substrate. The hydrogen-ion concentration of the reaction mixture was adjusted by addition of Walpole's acetate buffer (p_H 3.0–6.5). For high ranges of p_H , Sørensen's phosphate buffer was used. The enzyme solution was prepared by weighing a known amount of the enzyme powder, which was made into a paste with water and diluted to 100 c.c. It was prepared afresh for each experiment. The reactions were carried out at constant temperature in an electrically controlled thermostat.

The digestions were carried out in Erlenmeyer flasks with 100 c. c. lots of mixtures containing 1.5 g. of starch, buffer solution and enzyme. 10 C. c. samples were removed at intervals of 5, 10, 15, 20 and 30 minutes, and the reducing power determined by the method of Willstätter and Schudel (*Ber.*, 1918, 51, 780). The degree of hydrolysis is expressed by the reducing power of the mixture. This is measured by the amount of maltose formed in the total volume (100 c. c.) of the reaction mixture in a given time and the velocity constants for a unimolecular reaction were calculated according to Euler and Svanberg (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1920-21, 112, 191), by applying the formula

$$k = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$$

where t is the reaction time in minutes, a , the original concentration, x , the concentration of substrate decomposed and $a-x$, the concentration of the substrate present after t minutes. It was found that the unimolecular course of the reaction persists until 40–50 %

of the amount of maltose, formed on complete hydrolysis of the substrate, is present; on further hydrolysis, the rate of the reaction diminishes. The activity is given in terms of velocity constant k , and the activity unit (Sf) in terms of Euler's units.

Dialysis.—100 G. of powdered sweet potato meal was treated with 400 c. c. of distilled water in presence of toluene for about 16 hours at the laboratory temperature ($28-30^\circ$). It was then filtered, centrifuged, and dialysed in collodion tubes against distilled water containing toluene which was renewed twice every day. Each collodion tube contained 20 c. c. of the enzyme extract. At definite intervals of time one tube was taken out, centrifuged, and finally diluted to 100 c. c. The activity of this diluted enzyme solution was then determined.

The values thus obtained were compared with those for specimens of the original enzyme extract which had been left undialysed. It was found, however, that the activity of the undialysed enzyme remained practically unaltered during the experimental period.

For each trial, the reaction mixture contained 75 c.c. of 2 % soluble starch, 20 c.c. of acetate buffer adjusted to p_H 6.0 and 5 c.c. of enzyme solution. The temperature was $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. The results have been given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Dialysis.

Dialysed for.	Dry wt. enzyme soln. (g./5 c.c.).	Activity $k \times 10^4$.	Activity unit Sf (30°).
0 hr.	0.042	88.1	0.236
16	0.0050	68.3	1.536
40	0.0035	41.8	1.34
80	0.0031	29.6	1.11
120	0.0025	14.3	0.634

The results show that the activity per unit weight of dry substance of the enzyme (Sf) increases after 16 to 40 hours of dialysis to nearly seven times. Dialysis can, therefore, be very effectively used as one of the methods for the purification of the enzyme.

These observations correspond to those of Euler and Svanberg (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1921, 112, 193) and Holmberg, (*ibid.*, 1924, 134,

68) who used dialysis for the purification of malt and liver amylases respectively, and obtained products of greatly increased activity.

Influence of hydrogen ion concentration on the activity of the amylase.—Flasks containing 75 c. c. of 2 % soluble starch, 20 c. c. of buffer of varying hydrogen ion concentrations were kept in a thermostat at $35^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$. When the reaction mixture had attained the temperature of the thermostat, 5 c. c. of the enzyme solution (0.1 %) were added, and the activity measured. The results are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

Starch conc. = 1.5%. Enzyme conc. = 0.0005%.

p_H ...	8.0	7.1	6.5	6.2	6.0	5.5	5.3	4.8	4.6	4.2	3.0
Activity $k \times 10^4$...	25.8	53.4	82.1	90.3	114	114	96.9	91.4	76.7	52	25.7

It may be seen from the results that sweet potato amylase acts best in the region of p_H 5.5–6.0.

Influence of temperature on the activity of the amylase.—The reaction mixture consisting of 75 c.c. of 2 % soluble starch, 29 c. c. of buffer of p_H 6.0 and 5 c. c. of the enzyme solution (0.1 %) was maintained at temperatures of 20° , 30° , 35° , 40° , 50° , 55° , 60° and 70° in a thermostat and the activities measured. The results are presented in Table III.

TABLE III.

Starch conc. = 1.5%. Enzyme conc. = 0.005%. $p_H = 6.0$.

Temp. ...	20	30	35	40	45	50	55	60	70
Activity $k \times 10^4$...	39.4	79.7	99.5	117	134	150	151	125	24.9

The results show that the temperature optimum for sweet potato amylase lies in the region of 50° — 55° . Comparing this with the optimum for other amylases it may be noted that it is 45° for salivary amylase (Oppenheimer, "Die Fermente und ihre Wirkungen," Leipzig, 1903; König, *Biochem. Z.*, 1908, 10, 211), 35° for pancreatic amylase (Vermon, *J. Physiol.*, 1901-02, 27, 174), 40° for potato amylase (*Biochem. Z.*, 1914, 67, 166) and between 50 and 56° for amylases of germinated grains (Effront, *Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*,

1922, 86, 274; Patwardhan, *J. Ind. Inst. Sci.*, 1929, 12A, 185; Karmarkar and Patwardhan, *ibid.*, 1930, 13A, 159). It may be inferred, therefore, that potato amylase resembles animal amylases with regard to its temperature optimum, while the sweet potato amylase corresponds to cereal amylases.

Effect of temperature on the stability of sweet potato amylase.—In a previous communication on the heat inactivation of pancreatic amylase (Giri, *J. Ind. Inst. Sci.*, 1932, 15A, 117) it was stated that the process of heat inactivation follows a monomolecular course. The rate of inactivation of pancreatic amylase is minimum at a p_H 6.5 to 7.0 in the neighbourhood of the optimum reaction for the enzyme. Since the inactivation of enzymes by heat has a large temperature coefficient, it is possible that inactivation can take place at ordinary laboratory temperatures at slower rates. Thus, it was observed (Giri and Subrahmanyam, *ibid.*, 1932, 15A, 107) that vegetable amylases in aqueous solution lose their activity on ageing, and that they are most stable when maintained at their optimum p_H .

The following experiments were carried out in order to investigate the possibility of such inactivation (*vide*, Tables IVa and IVb).

(a) *Effect of temperature.*—10 C.c. of buffer mixtures (p_H 6.0) were kept in a thermostat at 50°, and when the temperature equilibrium was attained, 10 c.c. of 0.2% solution of the enzyme were added to each tube. At definite intervals of time 5 c.c. of the enzyme solution were pipetted out and the activity estimated at 30° and p_H 6.0. In a similar manner the inactivation of 0.1% amylase solution was carried at 60° and 65°. At higher temperatures the enzyme is very rapidly inactivated, so that the course of the reaction is difficult to follow. Simultaneously the activity of the enzyme solution of the same concentration which was kept at the room temperature (28°) was also determined. The experimental results are given in Table IVa.

From these experiments the value for the inactivation coefficient k_i is calculated from the equation

$$k_i = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{k_a}{k_t}$$

where k_a is the reaction constant of the enzyme which is not destroyed, and k_t is the reaction constant of the same enzyme which has been weakened in activity as the result of heating for t minutes.

TABLE IV a.

Temp.	Time of inactivation.	Activity at 30° of the amylase not destroyed by inactivation $k \times 10^4$.	$k_t = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{k_a}{k_t}$	k_t mean
50°	30 min.	68.9		
	60	68.9		
60°	10	62.8	0.00396	
	30	52.6	0.00388	0.0036
	60	43.9	0.00325	
65°	10	24.9	0.0220	
	30	14.3	0.0227	0.0216
	60	4.7	0.0200	
Control		68.8		

The results indicate that the process of heat inactivation of sweet potato amylase follows a monomolecular course. The enzyme is able to withstand increased temperature up to 50°. At 60° the loss in activity is under 50%, but at 65° it is about 80 % of the initial activity.

The destructive temperature of enzymes has been defined by Euler ("Chemie der Enzyme," 2nd Ed., 1922, p. 314) as that at which the activity of the enzyme is reduced 50% in 1 hour at the optimum p_H . The destructive temperature of sweet potato amylase lies therefore between 60° and 65°. Malt amylase is destroyed in one hour at 60° and its destructive temperature lies at 54°-56° (Ernström, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1922, 119, 190). Other plant amylases are more sensitive to temperature. Thus *phaseolus* amylase has its destructive temperature at 45° (Sjoberg, *Biochem. Z.*, 1923, 142, 274) and Doby (*loc. cit.*) found the destructive temperature of potato amylase to lie at 45°. Animal amylases are inactivated even at ordinary laboratory temperatures (Giri, *loc. cit.*).

Sweet potato amylase differs therefore from animal amylases and potato amylase but it resembles cereal amylases in its heat stability. The amylase can, in fact, withstand higher temperatures than malt amylase.

(b) *The effect of hydrogen ion concentration on the inactivation of the amylase.*—Acetate buffer mixtures (10 c.c.) of different hydrogen-ion concentrations were prepared and placed in a thermostat at 60°. When the temperature equilibrium was attained, 10 c.c. of 0.2% solution of the amylase was added into each test tube. One hour after the addition of the amylase, 5 c.c. samples were taken out and transferred to the reaction mixture containing 75 c.c. of 2% soluble starch and 20 c.c. of buffer of p_H 6.0. The activities were determined at 30° and are given in Table IVb.

TABLE IV b.

p_H ...	6.5	6.0	5.4	4.6
Activity of the amylase after heating at 60° for 60' ($k \times 10^4$) ...	20.5	38.9	39.4	4.7
Activity of the amylase without heating	79.0

The above experiments show that the stability of sweet potato amylase is greatest in the region of p_H , 5.4 and 6.0 which is also the optimum range of p_H for activity. Thus the optima for activity and stability are found to be at the same range of p_H . A similar observation was made on the ageing of amylases in aqueous solutions (Giri and Subrahmanyam, *loc. cit.*). Working on the heat inactivation of pancreatic amylase, Giri (*loc. cit.*) found that the rate of inactivation is minimum at p_H 6.5 to 7.0, in the neighbourhood of the optimum reaction for the enzyme. Comparing these with the observations of other workers, it may be noted that Lüers and Lorinzer (*Biochem. Z.*, 1932, 133, 487) found that the activity optimum and stability optimum for malt amylase was in the same range of hydrogen-ion concentration. Contrary to the observations of foregoing investigators Ernström (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1922, 119, 190) found the stability optimum at a higher p_H than the activity-optimum. In the case of ptyalin, Ernström found the stability optimum at p_H 6.0, *i. e.*, to the acid side of the optimum p_H for activity. This divergence can be easily explained in the

light of investigations of Michaelis and his co-workers (*Biochem. Z.*, 1911, 35, 386; 1914, 59, 77) who have shown that the activity- p_H curves for ptyalin vary according to the presence and nature of the neutral salts employed, and that these changes have been explained by the assumption of the formation of different amylase electrolyte complexes having different dissociation constants. The experiments of Ernström on the determination of stability optimum p_H and activity optimum p_H were not carried out at the same salt concentration, because sodium chloride was not added in the inactivation experiment, though the optimum p_H was determined in presence of the salt. Furthermore Myrback (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1926, 159, 1) has shown that the activity optimum of ptyalin lies at p_H 6.0 for NaCl-free ptyalin, and the stability optimum also lies at p_H 6.0 according to Ernström. So, it can be definitely said that the stability optimum and activity optimum lie at the same range of p_H for ptyalin, pancreatic amylase, malt amylase and sweet potato amylase.

Distribution of amylase in sweet potato.—The tuber was divided into the following portions.—(a) the outermost portion (representing a layer of about 1 cm. thickness from the surface); (b) the middle portion (representing the next immediate layer of about 1 cm. thickness); and (c) the innermost portion (representing the remaining part of the tuber, the core).

These different parts were chopped, dried in the sun and powdered. The enzyme was extracted from 5 g. of the powdered meal with 20 c.c. of water for 12 hours, filtered and centrifuged. The activities of these extracts (diluted 10 times) were then determined. The results are presented in Table V.

TABLE V.

75 C.c. of 2% soluble starch; 20 c.c. of buffer of p_H 6.0, 5 c.c. of the enzyme solution. (Total conc. of starch = 1.5% and the total volume = 100 c.c.).

	Dry in g./5 c.c. of the enzyme solution.	Activity $k \times 10^4$.
(a) Activity of the amylase in the outermost portion	0.0249	18.7
(b) Activity of the amylase in the middle portion	0.0235	46.1
(c) Activity of the amylase in the innermost portion	0.0239	62.4

The same experiment was repeated with the juice expressed from different portions of the same tuber. The results thus obtained were similar to those of the previous experiment. The results thus show that amylolytic activity increases as we pass from the skin to the interior and that the innermost portion has more than thrice the activity of the outermost portion.

The nature of sweet potato amylase.—According to Ohlsson and his co-workers (*Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*, 1922, 87, 1183; and *Compt. rend. Trav. Lab. Corlsberb.*, 1926, No. 7, 16; Nordh and Ohlsson, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1931-32, 204, 89; Ohlsson and Uddenberg, *ibid.*, 1933, 221, 165; Ohlsson and Edfeldt, *ibid.*, 1933, 221, 174) malt amylases of cereals consist of an α - or dextrinogen-amylase and of a β - or saccharogen-amylase, these being differentiated by studies of mutarotation as well as the relative hydrolysis as determined by changes in the iodine coloration and the reducing action. Nordh and Ohlsson (*loc. cit.*) and Myrback and Myrback (*Woch. Brau.*, 1932, 49, 246) have shown that ungerminated barley contains mostly only β -amylase whilst after germination considerable amounts of α -amylase is formed. Contrary to Nordh and Ohlsson's view, Waldschmidt Leitz, Reichel and Purr (*Naturwiss.*, 1932, 20, 254) have come to the conclusion that ungerminated barley contains both α - and β -amylases, but that the amylase is present in inactive form and requires amylokinase for activation. This kinase is developed during germination. Borchardt and Pringsheim (*loc. cit.*) working on the amylase, prepared from the press juice of the ground potato which was deproteinized with colloidal ferric hydroxide, have shown that the potato amylase apparently occupies an intermediate position between the malt amylase particularly rich in β -amylase and the taka amylase which is pure α -amylase, as it contains less β - than α -amylase. Willstätter and Rohdewald (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1933, 221, 13) have shown that the amylases of leucocytes are dextrinogenic in character, thereby resembling pancreatic amylase and differing from malt amylase. The foregoing observations bring out a distinct difference between animal and vegetable amylases, the former belonging to the class of α -amylases and the latter to that of β -amylases. According to Pringsheim, however, potato amylase falls midway between the two main classes.

The following experiments were, therefore, conducted with a view to throwing light on the nature of sweet potato amylase and to compare it with that of barley malt amylase. Amylase from barley

malt was prepared by extracting powdered malt (200 g.) with 800 c. c. of water for 24 hours in presence of toluene and finally filtered and centrifuged. To 400 c. c. of the filtrate 1600, c. c. of 95 % alcohol was slowly added with stirring and the precipitate allowed to settle during 6-8 hours when the alcohol was syphoned off, the rest of the liquid then centrifuged, and the sediment thus obtained washed and dehydrated with absolute alcohol and ether and finally dried in a desiccator over anhydrous calcium chloride.

Solutions (0.1 %) of the two amylases were prepared and the activities of the saccharogenic (S), and dextrinogenic components measured.

The activity of the saccharogen amylase (S) was determined as follows. 25 c. c. of 2% soluble starch was placed in a flask together with 10 c. c. of buffer solution (1/5M-acetic acid-acetate mixture). The flask was placed in a thermostat at 38°. When the solution had attained the temperature of the water, 5 c. c. of the enzyme solution were added. After 30 minutes, 10 c. c. were removed and the reducing value determined and expressed as mg. of maltose. The hydrogen-ion concentration of the reaction mixture was adjusted to p_H 4.6 for barley malt amylase, and p_H 6.0 for sweet potato amylase.

The activity of the dextrinogen amylase (X and Y) was determined according to Ohlsson (*loc. cit.*). The results are presented in Table VI.

TABLE VI.

	Activity of saccharogen amylase. (S)	Activity of dextrinogen amylase. (X) (Y)	
Sweet potato amylase	59	0	12
Barley malt amylase	68	24	190

The above figures show that sweet potato amylase is mainly a saccharogen amylase or β -amylase. Thus it differs from potato amylase and resembles barley amylase.

SUMMARY.

1. An active diastatic enzyme is present in sweet potato.
2. The enzyme can be prepared from the water extract of the dried meal followed by precipitation with alcohol. The preparation can

be further purified by dialysis as the result of which the activity is increased nearly seven times.

3. The optimum hydrogen ion concentration for the enzyme lies between p_H , 5.5–6.0.

4. The optimum temperature lies between 50° and 55°.

5. The process of heat inactivation of the amylase is found to follow a unimolecular course. The enzyme is most stable in the region of p_H 5.4 and 6.0, which is also the optimum range of p for activity.

6. The inner portion of the tuber possesses greater amylolytic activity than the layers near the surface.

7. The amylase is mainly a saccharogen amylase or β -amylase.

8. It resembles cereal amylases and differs from potato amylase as also similar enzymes of animal origin in all its characteristics.

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